

and Applications. Elsevier. 2022 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcr.2022.100067>

3. Arunima Ghosh, Shashank Gupta, Amit Dua, Neeraj Kumar. Security of Cryptocurrencies in blockchain technology: State-of-art, challenges and future prospects. Journal of Network and Computer Applications Elsevier. 2020.

4. Пашорін В. Технології безпеки криптовалюти та блокчейн-мережі. Зовнішня торгівля: економіка, фінанси, право. 2019. № 3 С. 93 – 101.

5. How is cryptocurrency changing money laundering? URL: <https://member.fintech.global/2022/05/03/how-is-cryptocurrency-changing-money-laundering/>

6. Europol spotlight. Cryptocurrencies: tracing the evolution of criminal finances. URL: <https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/Europol%20Spotlight%20-%20Cryptocurrencies%20%20Tracing%20the%20evolution%20of%20criminal%20finances.pdf>

7. The 2022 Crypto Crime Report. URL: <https://go.chainalysis.com/2022-Crypto-Crime-Report.html>

References

1. Zakon Ukrainy «Pro virtual'ni aktyvy». URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2074-20#Text>

2. Huaqun Guo Xingjie Yub. A survey on blockchain technology and its security. Blockchain: Research and Applications. Elsevier. 2022 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcr.2022.100067>

3. Arunima Ghosh, Shashank Gupta, Amit Dua, Neeraj Kumar. Security of Cryptocurrencies in blockchain technology: State-of-art, challenges and future prospects. Journal of Network and Computer Applications Elsevier. 2020.

4. Pashorin V. Tekhnolohiyi bezpeky kryptovalyuty ta blokcheyn-merezhi. Zovnishnya torhivlya: ekonomika, finansy, pravo. 2019. № 3 С. 93 – 101.

5. How is cryptocurrency changing money laundering? URL: <https://member.fintech.global/2022/05/03/how-is-cryptocurrency-changing-money-laundering/>

6. Europol spotlight. Cryptocurrencies: tracing the evolution of criminal finances. URL: <https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/Europol%20Spotlight%20-%20Cryptocurrencies%20%20Tracing%20the%20evolution%20of%20criminal%20finances.pdf>

7. The 2022 Crypto Crime Report. URL: <https://go.chainalysis.com/2022-Crypto-Crime-Report.html>

Дані про авторів

Мельник Тетяна Миколаївна,

д.е.н., професор, Державний торговельно-економічний університет, завідувач кафедри міжнародного менеджменту, Київ, Україна

e-mail: <http://t.melnyk@knute.edu.ua>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3839-6018>

Клим Олег Ігорович,

аспірант Державного торговельно-економічного університету, Київ, Україна

e-mail: o.klym@knute.edu.ua

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3134-9558>

Data about the authors

Tetiana Melnyk,

Doctor of Economics Sciences, Professor, State University of Trade and Economics, Head of the Department of International Management

e-mail: <http://t.melnyk@knute.edu.ua>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3839-6018>

Oleh Klym,

postgraduate, State University of Trade and Economics e-mail: o.klym@knute.edu.ua

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3134-9558>

УДК 005.572 (042.4)

MYKHAILOV A. M.
MYKHAILOV Y.O.

Improvement of management and administration of information and consulting services

Relevance of the research topic. The study of the issue of improving the management and administration of information and consulting services is conditioned by the lack of a single approach to the implementation of the algorithm of this process.

Formulation of the problem. In any field of human activity, problems of choice and management decisions arise continuously, which have become significantly more complicated in recent years due to the growth in scale and strengthening of interrelationships between individual sectors of the national economy. This fact actualizes the need to improve information support for making management decisions

using, including expert methods, in particular in the process of management and administration of information and consulting services, which determines the relevance of the research topic.

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – to investigate the issue of improving the management and administration of information and consulting services.

Research method or methodology. The article uses the following methods: monographic, analysis and synthesis, systematization.

Presentation of the main material (research results). It is proven that, taking into account the exceptional importance of reliable scientific support for radical market transformations, the creation and strengthening of a single market space in combination with the formation of regional markets, with the development of local self-government, there was an urgent need for a more in-depth study of the management and administration of information and consulting services.

Field of application of results. The results of the research can be used in the practical activities of enterprises, organizations and institutions to improve the management and administration of information and consulting services.

Conclusions on the article. The presented results of the research using the rating model in the evaluation of the management and administration of information and consulting services prove the feasibility of taking into account the typicality of the level and problems of socio-economic development, and the differentiation of measures by clusters when solving development priority issues within the framework of the formation of programs of socio-economic development.

Keywords: management, administration, information and consulting services, expert method, management decision-making.

МИХАЙЛОВ А.М.
МИХАЙЛОВ Є.О.

Вдосконалення управління і адміністрування інформаційно-консультаційних послуг

Актуальність теми дослідження. Дослідження питання вдосконалення управління і адміністрування інформаційно-консультаційних послуг обумовлюється відсутністю єдиного підходу до реалізації алгоритму даного процесу.

Постановка проблеми. У будь-якій сфері людської діяльності безперервно виникають проблеми вибору і прийняття управлінських рішень, які значно ускладнились в останні роки у зв'язку зі зростанням масштабів та посиленням взаємозв'язків між окремими ланками народного господарства. Даний факт актуалізує необхідність удосконалення інформаційного забезпечення прийняття управлінських рішень з використанням в т.ч. експертних методів, зокрема в процесі управління і адміністрування інформаційно-консультаційних послуг, що обумовлює актуальність теми дослідження.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – дослідити питання вдосконалення управління і адміністрування інформаційно-консультаційних послуг.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано наступні методи: монографічний, аналізу і синтезу, систематизації.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Доведено, що з урахуванням виняткової важливості достовірного наукового забезпечення радикальних ринкових перетворень, створення і зміцнення єдиного ринкового простору у поєднанні з формуванням регіональних ринків, з розвитком місцевого самоврядування, виникла гостра необхідність більш поглибленого вивчення управління і адміністрування інформаційно-консультаційних послуг.

Галузь застосування результатів. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані в практичній діяльності підприємств, організацій та установ для вдосконалення управління і адміністрування інформаційно-консультаційних послуг.

Висновки за статтю. Представлені результати дослідження з використанням рейтингової

моделі при оцінці управління і адміністрування інформаційно–консультаційних послуг доводять доцільність врахування типовості рівня та проблем соціально–економічних розвитку, та диференціації заходів по кластерам при вирішенні питань пріоритетності розвитку в рамках формування Програм соціально–економічного розвитку.

Ключові слова: управління, адміністрування, інформаційно–консультаційні послуги, експертний метод, прийняття управлінських рішень.

Statement of the problem in a general form and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. In any field of human activity, problems of choice and management decisions arise continuously, which have become significantly more complicated in recent years due to the growth in scale and strengthening of interrelationships between individual sectors of the national economy. Due to the rapidity of social processes and the limitation of information arrays on this basis, significant problems have arisen with the use of formal research methods. However, no matter what problems arise with the use of the methodological apparatus of research, in production management, they are constantly faced with a set of alternative solutions and the need to choose the optimal solution among them. Therefore, the practical value of expert methods, which recently play a significant role in management, and sometimes become the only method of analysis, preparation, justification and selection of optimal solutions, became more acutely realized everywhere. When evaluating alternative solutions and choosing the best (optimal) solution, experts become a kind of «sources of insufficient information», which is the result of specialists' knowledge, intuition, and finally experience. It should be noted that information received from specialists plays the same role in expert methods as statistical, operational and other types of quantitative information in formal methods. This fact actualizes the need to improve information support for making management decisions using, including expert methods, in particular in the process of management and administration of information and consulting services, which determines the relevance of the research topic.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, in which the solution to this problem was initiated and on which the author relies, selection of previously unsolved parts of the general problem, to which the article is devoted. The beginning of the formation of expert evaluation of information and consulting services is the American scientific school of the

20th century [1; 2; 7]. There are two main types of expert evaluations – individual and collective. Individual – these are assessments of one specialist, and collective – assessments of an expert commission. There are also single–round and multi–round evaluations, with and without information exchange, anonymous and open. When classifying by a number of tasks to be solved, evaluation and management examinations are distinguished [3; 8]. In general, expert evaluations are the judgments of highly qualified professionals, presented in the form of substantive, qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the object, intended for use in decision–making.

The main methods of examination of information and consulting services include: methods of creating collective decisions, methods of structuring, methods of expert evaluations, morphological methods, methods of complex examinations. In many cases, the best effect is the complex application of several types of expertise.

In the modern world, as a result of scientific and technical progress, special attention is paid to qualitative aspects of changes in forecasting and strategic analysis. The growth trends of these changes determined, as evidenced by the review of literary sources, an increase in the specific weight of expert forecasting methods to approximately 40–50% [2; 9].

Therefore, the growth of qualitative changes contributes to the development and improvement of expert methods of forecasting the consequences of information and consulting services and at the same time narrows the possibility of using accurate calculations based on formalized models that reflect the variety of cause–and–effect relationships of the evolution of phenomena (processes, objects).

Summarizing what has been said, it can be stated with all certainty that the methods of expert evaluations in forecasting the consequences of information and consulting services are used in the following cases: in the absence of sufficient and reliable information about the forecasted phenomena (processes, objects); in conditions of significant uncertainty of

the environment where the facility operates; in conditions of time shortage or extreme situations; in the development of medium- and long-term forecasts of objects that are subject to radical changes, for example, scientific discoveries [4; 5; 6; 10].

Thus, the use of expert methods of supporting management decision-making in the practice of information and consulting services is an objective necessity due to the significant complication of the socio-economic processes of the development of society and the shortage of sources of quality information. The effectiveness of the management and administration of information and consulting services depends on the correct organization of the process and processing of the received information.

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – to investigate the issue of improving the management and administration of information and consulting services.

Presentation of the main material of the study with a full justification of the obtained scientific results. In order to evaluate statistical indicators that cannot be compared in the usual way (mathematically), it is necessary to carry out a preliminary assessment of statistical indicators using the point method, with the assignment of an assessment based on an individual position (place) in the series of data, and to use a comparative analysis in the form of a rating.

The prototype of the proposed model is the sum of places method [7, 8]. With this approach, the analyzed information and consulting services must be practically identical, otherwise the comparison will be incorrect. The essence of the proposed model is the use of rating evaluation of information and consulting services and scoring methods for evaluation and grouping of disparate statistical data.

A common feature with the prototype is that the method of ranking information and consulting services on a set of indicators based on individual rating assessments was used. It differs in that, in the proposed model, the method of the sum of places is extended by using the method of points and allows taking into account the variation factor when grouping statistical indicators.

The basis of the proposed model is the task of developing a method of analyzing heterogeneous statistical data when solving the tasks of assessing the achieved level of development based on the results of the provision of information and consulting services.

The evaluation uses a 7-point scale, taking into account the favorable trend of changing indicators:

outsider	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	leader
-----------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---------------

The maximum number of points – 7 points is assigned to the object with the maximum value of the indicator in the aggregate, as well as to objects whose indicator values are within the range of the assessment. Intermediate grades are assigned according to the same principle. At the same time, the object with the minimum value of the indicator is assigned 1 point. In this way, some grouping of statistical indicators is achieved. The step of ranges is calculated by the formula:

$$Step = \frac{max-min}{Bal_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where *Step* – is the interval step;

max – the maximum value of the evaluated indicator;

min – the minimum value of the evaluated indicator;

Bal_{max} – is the maximum value of the score.

The interpretation of the score is carried out in accordance with the expert assessment. After evaluating each indicator as a whole, the average values for three groups of components of sustainable development are calculated and in the end – a generalizing indicator – indicator of sustainable development.

The research uses the concept of «harmonious development» along with the concept of «sustainability». In fact, this concept characterizes the community of directions of development. Economic growth in its essence should cause the rise of the social sphere, and since man is a part of nature and biologically connected to it to ensure his survival, he should take care of the ecological state, which is facilitated by the provision of information and consulting services. On the contrary, the poor state of the environment and the underdevelopment of the social sphere lead to a deterioration in the health of the population and a decrease in the work motivation of employees. Therefore, the higher the indicator of harmonious development together with the stability indicator, the more resistant the system is to all kinds of disturbances. To calculate the sustainability indicator, the methodology for measuring sustainable development proposed by the Institute of Applied System Analysis of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine and the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine [3] is used.

According to the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, sustainable development is assessed using the appropriate I_{sd} index in the space of three measurements: economic I_{ecn} , environmental I_{ecl} and social I_{scl} . This index is a vector whose norm determines the level of sustainable development, and its spatial position in the coordinate system I_{ecn} , I_{ecl} , I_{scl} characterizes the degree of «harmony» of this development (the degree of harmonization of sustainable development I_{gd}). Equidistant vector I_{sd} from each of the coordinates I_{ecn} , I_{ecl} , I_{scl} will correspond to the greatest harmony of sustainable development. The approach of this vector to one of the coordinates will indicate the priority development according to the corresponding measurement and the neglect of the other two. The index I_{sd} and the degree of harmonization of sustainable development I_{gd} are calculated according to the calculated I_{ecn} , I_{ecl} , I_{scl} .

At the same time, it was taken into account that all data, indicators and indices included in the model are measured using different physical quantities, have different interpretations and change in different ranges. In order to bring the values to a single measurement system, the algorithm for assigning a score to statistical indicators, presented earlier, was used.

By the degree of harmonization of sustainable development, we mean the angle between the vector I_{sd} and the norm:

$$\|I_{sd}\| = \sqrt{(I_{ecn}^2 + I_{ecl}^2 + I_{scl}^2)} \quad (2)$$

An ideal vector that is equidistant from each of the coordinates I_{ecn} , I_{ecl} , I_{scl} with the norm:

$$\|1\| = \sqrt{(1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2)} \quad (3)$$

This angle is measured in degrees and determined by the ratio:

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{I_{ecn} + I_{ecl} + I_{scl}}{\sqrt{3} \cdot \sqrt{I_{ecn}^2 + I_{ecl}^2 + I_{scl}^2}} \quad (4)$$

It varies within the limits:

$$0 \leq \alpha \leq \alpha_{\max}; \alpha_{\max} = \arccos \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

As this angle approaches 0, the degree of harmonization of sustainable development will increase. For the convenience of comparison in terms of the degree of harmonization of sustainable development, we will reduce this indicator to the following normalized form:

$$I_{gd} = \frac{\hat{G} - G_{\min}}{G_{\max} - G_{\min}}, \text{ де} \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{G} = 1 - \frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{\max}}; G_{\max} = 1 - \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_{\max}}; G_{\min} = 1 - \frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_{\max}}$$

$$\alpha_1 = 0; \alpha_2 = \frac{45}{\pi} \cdot \arccos \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

As a result of applying this normalization, the degree of I_{gd} harmonization will vary in the range [0–1]. It will increase as I_{gd} approaches 1 and decrease as I_{gd} approaches 0. Thus, the MVSR model allows calculating the index of sustainable development I_{sd} and the degree of harmonization of this development I_{gd} any consequence of the use of information and consulting services for which there are data, obtained as a result of assigning grades to statistical indicators.

The system of indicators basically has a two-level classification, in which the first level of classification characterizes groups of indicators in relation to resources, the second level – branch affiliation:

I. Development of potential:

1. State support for development (6 indicators).
2. Production potential (15 indicators).
3. Infrastructure (5 indicators).
4. Demographic stability (18 indicators).
5. Health care (7 indicators).

II. Effective development:

6. Technological development (23 indicators).
7. Effectiveness of market development (9 indicators).
8. Development of the labor market (9 indicators).
9. Social support for development (26 indicators).
10. Development of the educational system (4 indicators).

11. Effectiveness of the legal system (6 indicators).

III. Sustainability:

12. Environmental protection (3 indicators).
13. Innovative development (2 indicators).

The ratio of assessments by individual categories allows us to draw a conclusion about development priorities (Table).

To obtain information about the stage of management and administration of information and consulting services on the way to sustainability, all components are divided into groups for three characteristic types of economy.

The presented results of the study using a useful model in the evaluation of statistical indicators prove the feasibility of taking into account the typicality of the level and problems of socio-economic development, and the differentiation of measures

Table 1. Classification of objects by stages of development in the system of management and administration of information and consulting services

Stage	Rating	Aspects of development
Stage 1 (development due to potential)	More than 3 points	Availability of resource potential is crucial, technological aspects are important
Transition from stage 1 to stage 2	More than 4 points	The availability of resource potential and the importance of the growing technological component are of decisive importance The availability of resource potential is important, the main emphasis is on the development of the technological component
Stage 2 (focus on efficient production and minimizing the use of resources)	More than 5 points	The same as in the previous one, but the importance of innovative factors of technological development is growing
Transition from stage 2	More than 5 points	All three components are important: resource potential, technological, innovative and environmental factors

by clusters when solving development priority issues within the framework of the formation of programs of socio-economic development.

Thus, the given data testify to the expediency of using the presented method for evaluating phenomena that have heterogeneous units of measurement of statistical data, because it allows taking into account all the characteristics of development indicators (ecological, social, etc.), which cannot be compared in the usual way (mathematically). An additional advantage for the management and administration of information and consulting services is that it is provided with a comprehensive assessment with reflection in social, economic and environmental processes. Establishing relevant changes in parameters in this case will provide an opportunity to analyze the sensitivity of the socio-economic system to these changes both in terms of local progress (in indices and sub-indices) and in the balancing and unbalancing of the development of the system.

Conclusions

Maintaining the necessary proportions in the economy, preventing excessive differentiation according to the level of socio-economic development, ensuring the effective functioning of the market are the most important aspects of the modernization of the economy and its sustainable development. Taking into account the exceptional importance of reliable scientific support for radical market transformations, the creation and strengthening of a single market space in combination with the formation of regional markets, with the development of local self-government, there was an urgent need for a more in-depth study of the management and administration of information and consulting services. Today is characterized by signifi-

cant information complexity due to the need to combine multi-level plans and cross-sectoral characteristics (ecological, economic and social spheres). Moreover, individual areas of planning do not have information support regarding development prospects. All this creates conditions for the involvement of expert methods in the information management and administration of information and consulting services. One of the convenient forms of presentation of research results using expert methods are ratings, which can be used as a means of monitoring socio-economic processes and benchmarks for long-term strategic planning. The presented results of the research using the rating model in the evaluation of the management and administration of information and consulting services prove the feasibility of taking into account the typicality of the level and problems of socio-economic development, and the differentiation of measures by clusters when solving development priority issues within the framework of the formation of programs of socio-economic development.

Список використаних джерел

1. Гонтарева І. В. Консалтингові послуги в сфері підприємництва. Харків: ХНЕУ, 2016. 136 с.
2. Жорняк А. Інформаційна послуга у сфері господарювання: поняття та ознаки. Підприємництво, господарство і право. 2019. №10. С. 61–65.
3. Спільник І. В., Загородна О. М., Ярощук О. В. Консультаційна діяльність: актуальність, особливості та перспективи розвитку. Економічний аналіз. 2018. Том 28. № 3. С. 192–198.
4. Brockova K., Rossokha V., Chaban V., Zos-Kior M., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. Economic mechanism of optimizing the innovation investment program of the development of agro-industrial production. Management

Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development. 2021. Vol. 43. No. 1. P. 129–135.

5. Hnatenko I., Kuksa I., Prokopenko O., Naholiuk O. Management bases of modeling of business development state priorities: motivational–cognitive, socio–economic, stereotypical–behavioral factors. Вісник Черкаського університету. Серія «Економічні науки». Випуск 3. 2021. С. 58–64.

6. Kuksa I., Hnatenko I., Kolomoiets Y., Mykhailov S. Modeling of State Priorities of Management in the Conditions of Globalization: Financial, Technical–technological and Resource Aspects. Економічні горизонти. 2021. №1. С. 21–29.

7. Rakhmetulina Z., Pokataieva O., Trokhymets O., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. Optimization of the structure of an innovative cluster on a competitive basis in a free market. Financial and credit activities: problems of theory and practice. 2020. Vol. 4. №35. P. 238–247.

8. M.O. Sokolov, A.M. Mykhailov, N.V. Stoyanets, A.O. Klymchuk. Management of Innovation and Investment Development of Agricultural Economy of Ukraine in the Context of Globalization and Sustainable Development. International Journal of Ecological Economics & Statistics, 2019, Volume: 40, Issue Number: 3 P.1–15.

9. Stolyarov V., P6sztorov6 J., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Petchenko M. Optimization of material and technical supply management of industrial enterprises. Naukovyi Visnyk Natsionalnoho Hirnychoho Universytetu. 2022. № 3(189). P. 163–167.

10. Zhyvko Z., Nikolashyn A., Semenets I., Karpenko Y., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Klymenchukova N., Krakhmalo–va N. Secure aspects of digitalization in management accounting and finances of the subject of the national economy in the context of globalization. Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design. 2022. Vol. 39. P. 259–269.

References

1. Gontareva I. V. (2016). Consulting services in the field of entrepreneurship. Kharkiv: Khneu, 136 с.

2. Zhornyak A. (2019). Information service in the field of management: concepts and features. Entrepreneurship, economy and law, 10, 61–65.

3. Splinnyk I.V., Zagorodna O.M., Yaroschuk O.V. (2018). Consulting activity: relevance, features and development prospects. Economic analysis, 28.3, 192–198.

4. Brockova K., Rossokha V., Chaban V., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. (2021). Economic mechanism of optimizing the innovation investment program of the development of agro–industrial production. Management Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development, 43.1, 129–135.

5. Hnatenko I., Kuksa I., Prokopenko O., Naholiuk O. (2021). Management bases of modeling of business development state priorities: motivational–cognitive, socio–economic, stereotypical–behavioral factors, Visnyk Cherkas'koho universytetu. Seriya «Ekonomiczni nauky» [Bulletin of Cherkasy University. Economic Sciences Series], 3, 58–64.

6. Kuksa I., Hnatenko I., Kolomoiets Y., Mykhailov S. (2021). Modeling of state priorities of management in the conditions of globalization: financial, technical–technological and resource aspects. Ekonomichni horyzynty [Economic Horizons], 1, 21–29.

7. Rakhmetulina Z., Pokataieva O., Trokhymets O., Hnatenko I., Rubezhanska V. (2020). Optimization of the structure of an innovative cluster on a competitive basis in a free market. Financial and Credit Activities: Problems of Theory and Practice, 4.35, 238–247.

8. Sokolov M.O., Mykhailov A.M., Stoyanets N.V., Klymchuk A.O. (2019). Management of Innovation and Investment Development of Agricultural Economy of Ukraine in the Context of Globalization and Sustainable Development. International Journal of Ecological Economics & Statistics, 40.3, 1–15.

9. Stolyarov V., P6sztorov6 J., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Petchenko M. (2022). Optimization of material and technical supply management of industrial enterprises. Naukovyi Visnyk Natsionalnoho Hirnychoho Universytetu, 3(189), 163–167.

10. Zhyvko Z., Nikolashyn A., Semenets I., Karpenko Y., Zos–Kior M., Hnatenko I., Klymenchukova N., Krakhmalo–va N. (2022). Secure aspects of digitalization in management accounting and finances of the subject of the national economy in the context of globalization. Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design, 39, 259–269.

Дані про авторів

Михайлов Андрій Миколайович,

д.е.н., професор, менеджер з логістики, Deutsche Post AG DHL, м. Мюльдорф на Інн, Баварія, Німеччина

Михайлов Євген Олександрович,

комп'ютерний технік, Laptop Markt | Brese GmbH м. Кюмельсбрук, Верхній Пфальц, Німеччина

Data about the authors

Andrii Mykhailov,

Dr. Sc. (Econ), Professor, Manager of Logistics, Deutsche Post AG DHL, Germany, Bayern, Mьldorf am Inn

Yevhen Mykhailov,

Computer technician, Laptop Markt | Brese GmbH, Germany, Upper Palatinate, Kьmmersbruck